

ARKLOW BYPASS - DESIGN AND CONSTRUCTION

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Synopsis:

This paper describes the identification of the need for a road bypass of Arklow, and how a dual carriageway[®] road scheme was developed and implemented to meet that need. It gives details of innovations brought to the project, including a major steel/concrete composite bridge over the Avoca river and the use of coated precast concrete piles in contaminated ground. The project is 11.5km in length and necessitated 13 major structures.

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LEGEND:

○	ARKLOW BYPASS ROUTE
○	INDICATES UNDERBRIDGE
○	INDICATES OVERBRIDGE
⑬	COOLADANGAN ROAD
①	COOLADANGAN RAIL
②	SOUTHERN INTERCHANGE
③	COOLGREANEY ROAD
④	JOHNSTOWN ROAD
⑤	LAMBERTON ACCESS
⑥	VALE ROAD
⑦	VALE ROAD RAIL
⑧	AVOCA RIVER
⑩	IFI ACCESS
⑪	BEECH ROAD
⑫	NORTHERN INTERCHANGE
⑬	RUGBY CLUB

Figure 1 Plan of bypass

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Need for the Scheme

The town of Arklow is situated on the Wicklow coast, where the Avoca River enters the sea, and lies on the N11, Dublin to Wexford National Primary Road. As far back as 1968, it was recognised (Ref 1) that there was a severe traffic congestion problem in the town, especially at weekends during the summer season. Traffic management and parking measures were recommended as an immediate means of alleviating the problems of the time. However, it was also recognised that a bypass of the town would be needed in the medium term to deal with projected traffic increases anticipated within the town and on the N11. Provision for a bypass was made in the Wicklow County Development Plan (1989), in the Arklow Urban Development Plan (1991), and in 'Ireland - Road Development 1989-1993', the Operational Programme for Roads, which formed a part of the "National

Development Plan 1989-1993".

In 1990, when the scheme was being moved forward to design stage, the annual average traffic flows north and south of Arklow were approximately 6000 vehicles per day. Seasonal variations could add up to 40% to these figures, and during the month of August it was noted that the peak hour traffic on Friday evenings was as much as 20% of the Average Annual Daily Traffic. It was predicted that the construction of a bypass would remove up to 55% of through traffic from the town.

The provision of the bypass is in accord with the objectives of the Wicklow County Development Plan, although its construction did conflict to some degree with the conservation policies of the County Development Plan in respect to a small area of woodlands at Glenart Wood.

Preliminary Stage - Route Appraisal

The introduction of Computer Aided Design enabled a large number of alternative alignments to be considered and in this instance twenty five different possible routes were examined, within a western corridor, together with a possible route to the east of Arklow, on the seaward side. From these 26 routes Wicklow County Council design staff identified 5 possible viable routes, all of which lay within the western corridor. At the end of 1991 Wicklow County Council

appointed ESBI-Atkins to prepare an Environmental Impact Statement for the scheme. The EIS was prepared in two stages. The first, a route selection report was published in May 1992, and recommended a single route option, based on a thorough analysis of the relevant criteria, including environmental effects, costs, alignment standards, and traffic considerations.

The preferred option was approved by the County Council and Arklow Urban District Council in the summer of 1992. ESBI-Atkins then proceeded to produce the full EIS on the preferred route.

Appointment of Consultants- Detailed Design

In May 1992, following an interview and selection procedure, Ove Arup and Partners Ireland were appointed as consultants to Wicklow County Council for the detail design, preparation of contract documents and supervision of construction for the bypass scheme.

In the autumn of 1992 difficulties became apparent with ground conditions where the alignment of the bypass crossed over a disused gypsum pond on the lands of Irish Fertiliser Industries. The route was slightly modified locally to avoid the area. The EIS was extended to deal with this amendment.

Public Inquiry

The Environmental Impact Statement was published by Wicklow County Council in May 1993, at the same time as the Compulsory Purchase Order (CPO) for the lands necessary to construct the scheme. A small number of objections was received, and a Public Local Inquiry into the EIS and CPO was held in September 1993. The Inspector queried the provision of an at-grade junction for two landowners rather than a grade separa-

Figure 2 Alternative routes considered

rated junction, and suggested that Wicklow County Council should consider this option again. Wicklow County Council then prepared a second CPO which was necessary to acquire the land required for a new grade separated junction at the southern end of the scheme. This CPO was published in November 1993. One objection was received, and a second Public Inquiry was held in February 1994.

The Minister for the Environment confirmed both of the CPOs and the EIS in May 1994. Iarnród Éireann (IE) objected to the High Court that the Minister did not have a legal right to acquire lands from them. In order to avoid protracted legal proceedings a compromise was reached in which the Local Authority agreed not to pursue acquisition provided IE allowed Wicklow County Council to construct bridges over the railway at the two locations necessary for the construction of the bypass. Following the withdrawal of all objections the CPO became operative in September 1994.

2.0 THE SITE

Geology

The underlying rock is a Lower Silurian deposit which consists of siltstone, sandstone, slates and shales. From an engineering point of view it is generally thinly bedded weak rock. Bedrock is encountered in the two cuts south of the Avoca River and for a section immediately north of the Avoca.

The deep channel of the Avoca is the main geological feature along the route. With rock outcrops to the north and south, the bedrock dips steeply to a valley some 25 m below present river level. This valley has been filled with river gravels, which have been eroded and redeposited in channels and more recently by soft alluvial deposits. Interestingly, similar alluvial deposits were found to contain gold lumps creating a mini gold-rush in 1795 in the valley area west of Woodenbridge. Unfortunately no gold was unearthed in this project.

The soil deposits north and south of the river are generally a clay rich till, the one exception being a mixed sand and gravel deposit north of the Avoca River valley.

Site Investigations

The site investigations were carried out in a series of stages reflecting progress in preliminary and detail design, and the needs of the EIS. A Preliminary Ground Investigation in the Avoca Valley was carried out in Autumn 1990 by IGSL to assist in evaluating the preliminary routes. A more detailed preliminary ground investigation on the preferred route in the Avoca Valley was carried out by Geotech Limited in 1993, and this was followed by the main site investigation for the route, also carried out by Geotech in 1993. A more detailed site investigation, including investigations for the foundations for

the main Avoca bridge was carried out by Site Investigations Limited, in 1993 and early 1994.

A structural assessment of the existing railway bridge at Cooladangan was carried out by Arup with the assistance of Fleeton Watson Limited in late 1993.

The site investigation was presented as a series of reports which were prepared for each cut section, each fill section and each structure. The factual data was compiled and composite plots provided for each section to assist contractors for the main works in making their interpretation of the ground conditions.

Additional Trials

In order to fully assess the ground conditions and the difficulties which a contractor might face in constructing the project, trials of various construction expedients were carried out and their viability for the site proven in advance of the main contract.

The Avoca River crossing was clearly the most difficult section of the alignment. Rock extended to depths of over 20 m in places and was overlain by boulder clay, variable sand and gravel deposits, and alluvial clays and peat. In addition, waste containing varying contaminants was located in the made ground above the alluvium north of the river. In order to assess the best means of constructing both the embankments and bridge piles over the soft sometimes contaminated ground a series of trials was undertaken and are shown in Table 1.

A trial excavation to assess the feasibility of the use of an 'excavate-and-replace' technique was carried out by Hanleys of Roscommon in Autumn 1993, on the soft ground areas immediately south of the Avoca river. Murphy International carried out trial piling contracts in the Avoca Valley to confirm characteristics of driving steel

and precast concrete piles. These tests were also used to evaluate the suitability of precast concrete piles coated with 'Consokote' protective coating for use in the aggressive ground conditions which had been found in the area immediately north of the Avoca river, and which had their origin in the disposal of the by-products of the production of fertilisers. A 'Vertical Drain' trial was carried out by Hambra Construction to assess the feasibility of driving vertical drains through overlying shale capping or iron oxide and carbon black deposits above soft peat and alluvium layers encountered in the vicinity of the IFI canal. A trial construction of hard standing in the Avoca valley was carried out successfully by Stephen Byrne, Contractors, in November 1992, and a second enabling contract on the other side of the Avoca was carried out by Cedar Builders in December 1993.

Archaeology

A survey carried out on behalf of ESBI-Atkins at the time of preparing the EIS identified 12 sites which would be affected by the construction of the bypass, as well as two other possible sites which could not be exactly located before the work would commence. The principal sites were three sections of King James Road, Johnstown South Ringfort, and a group of Fulacht Fiadh or Bronze Age

cooking sites. At that stage it was believed that none of these sites was of particular importance, although an undertaking was given that Johnstown Ringfort could be fully excavated before work commenced in that area. In the event, it was found that the Johnstown site was of great national importance, and much wider in extent than anticipated.

3.0 ROUTE ALIGNMENT

Route Description

All chainage measurements were referred to the commencing point of the bypass which lies just inside the Wexford county boundary south of Arklow. Chainages therefore increase in a northerly direction from this point. The route crosses the Dublin -Wexford rail line at CH. 1350 at a very oblique angle, which meant that only part of the new widened carriageways could be fitted over the existing rail bridge. In addition, to allow for possible future electrification of the rail service, the road alignment was raised over the full width of the new construction. A local access at Cooladangan is provided for a number of farms by means of a substantial underpass constructed to full bridge specifications in order to give access to residential properties in the area which were affected, and to meet the visibility requirements. The Southern

Interchange is located at CH.1730, and gives access to the existing old Arklow Road(N11), and to the local road network.

From the Southern Interchange the road sweeps in cut through a local ridge, towards the northwest, and parallel to a local stream, crossing the Coolgreaney Road and the Johnstown Road and the Coolgreaney stream on a very substantial embankment, up to 18 metres in height. It then goes into cut before passing under the Lamberton Avenue bridge and emerging on embankment into the Avoca valley. The route crosses over the Vale Road at CH.5645 and then immediately over the railway once again, and then on a continuing high embankment to the edge of the Avoca flood plain. The crossing of the Avoca Valley is described in Section 4.

Rising out of the Avoca Valley the route is carried on embankment over soft ground and into a major cutting where it passes under a realigned access road to the IFI plant, and under Beech Road, and thence still in cut to the Northern Interchange at CH.8500. This interchange provides a connection to the Redcross Road and to the old N11 Arklow road. The route then passes to the east of the old road, more or less at existing ground level until it rejoins the existing N11

No	Test	Date	Contractor	Purpose
1	Excavation & Replacement	8/93	Hanley Borthers	Assess practicability of method south of river
2	Trial Piling ¹	4/94	Murphy International	Compare driving and capacity precast concrete and steel H piles
3	Ground Resistivity	9/94	Arup R & D	Assess requirements of cathodic protection system for steel piles
4	Vertical Drains	2/95	Hambra	Assess drivability of vertical drains through hard
5	Trial Piling ²	9/95	Murphy International	Compare corrosion systems for treated precast concrete and tubular steel piles

Table 1 Construction Trials

north of Arklow Rugby Club at CH.11600.

Design Parameters

The main route is designed as a full specification Dual Carriageway, in accordance with the requirements of RT180 (ref 2) with a design speed of 100KPH. The basic cross-section has a width of 34 metres, comprising, on either side of the centreline, a verge of 2.0 metres, 3.0m hard shoulder, 2 x 3.75m traffic lanes, 1.0m paved edge strip, and 3.5m grassed median. A working space of 4.0m has been allowed at top and bottom of all slopes. Sideslopes are generally at 1 on 2, except where less steep slopes were necessary for aesthetic reasons. Arising from experiences on this contract, and similar experiences elsewhere, it has been shown that 2.0 metres is no longer an adequate width of verge. With the demands of multiple IT service providers, in addition to those of all the other services such as water, electricity, gas, etc, and the need for safety barriers on all embankments exceeding 2.0 m in height on high speed roads, a verge width of 3.0 metres should be provided wherever possible.

Road Cross - Sections

Figures 3 and 4 show the road cross - sections adopted for the mainline and for the secondary connecting link roads.

Signposting and Road Marking

Road signs and the road marking design are in accordance with the Irish Road Sign Manual (ref 3).

Road Safety Audit

A full three stage road safety audit was carried out on the entire scheme by an independent safety audit group from Ove Arup and Partners, Cardiff. Arising from the preliminary stage audit, and the first visit by the audi-

Figure 3 Mainline road cross-section

Figure 4 Side-road cross section

tors to the site, a number of improvements, particularly in regard to sight distance requirements, was incorporated into the design. The third, or final stage, audit was carried out just prior to the opening, and all necessary minor changes identified or items which might possibly pose a risk to road users were acted upon.

Earthworks Reuse Clays tills/marl

The soil deposits generally consisted of glacial clays. These tills tended to have a much higher fines (silt and clay) fraction than typical Irish tills, as illustrated on Figure 3.7. in the attached appendix. In addition the plasticity characteristics (which reflects their sensitivity to changes in moisture content) are also highly variable (see Figure 3.8). Given the high clay content and the high moisture contents of the soil it was anticipated that a significant amount of excavation would prove unsuitable for reuse. Two of the charts used to assess suitability of the clays are shown on Figure 3.9a and b. The strength-moisture content plot of Figure 3.9a shows a number of samples with high moisture contents, and CBR values below 2. A preference for a suitability criterion based

on the optimum moisture content was expressed by the NRA. Our statistical analysis of Figure 3.9b showed that using a criterion of 1.3 times optimum moisture content was most representative of a CBR=2 value. However it should be noted that a significant number of samples gave CBR=2 results at much lower than 1.3 times the optimum moisture content.

Sands and Gravels

The occurrences of sand and gravel in the proposed cuts were few, with the exception of Cut 3 just north of the River Avoca. The site investigation had shown this area to contain highly variable layers of sands, gravels and

silts some of which were water bearing. For this reason the material was not expected to produce satisfactory capping material and the tender documents reflected this.

Rock Excavation

As discussed in Section 2 the local rock was generally weak, thinly bedded shaley siltstone, sandstones and mudstone (argillaceous). Testing showed the rock generally did not meet typical specifications for capping material. The tender documents reflected this by stating its non-suitability as capping and by altering the definition of rock to include this easily excavated material. It was proposed to reuse the rock in areas of high embankments and as a layering material within poorer clay fills.

High Embankments

The embankment crossing the Coolgreaney stream was approximately 18 m high. Given the expectation of relatively poor clayey fill material for embankment construction there was concern over the stability of the embankment. A series of slope stability analyses was carried out (Figure 3.5) in attached appendix, which show the effects of soil strength and embankment height on stability. For this reason the lower section of the embankment was specified to be constructed using the locally won shale rock. An adequate safety factor on stability could be achieved using this rockfill base. However, it did require the contractor to programme his works to minimise double handling of materials, in that he would have to excavate and place clay soils from the adjacent cut prior to exposing the rock in that cut.

4.0 BRIDGES

The project required the construction of a total of 13 bridges, excluding farm access structures, classified as follows;

- 4 Overbridges
- 6 underbridges
- Bridge over River Avoca
- 2 bridges over the Dublin to Wexford rail line

In developing the preliminary designs for the bridges on the scheme, a very conscious effort was made to develop a common theme, especially in regard to detailing and concrete finishes. Extensive physical modelling of deck and pier elements was employed, in addition to computer aided visualisations.

Due to the prominent visibility of the overbridges to motorists travelling on

the N11, careful thought was given to the form and finish of the piers.

Overbridges

Three of the overbridges consist of a two span configuration with a central pier located within the mainline median. The decks are of cast insitu cellular post tensioned construction.

The remaining overbridge is a four span cast insitu reinforced concrete

deck with piers located within the central median and on both verges.

Underbridges

All the underbridges consist of single span structures over local roads. The spans range from 12.5m up to 26.5m. All the decks are of precast U or T beam construction with full height abutments, except for Vale Road bridge which has a cast insitu cellular post tensioned deck.

Avoca Valley Crossing Conforming Tender Design

The conforming tender design for the crossing of the Avoca Valley consisted of 5 basic elements.

- An embankment transition zone from the soft approach embankment 'excavate-and-replace section' to the bridge.
- A 5 span cast insitu cellular post tensioned bridge over the Avoca River to be constructed off false work.
- A piled embankment over the IFI landfill site just north of the river.
- A reinforced concrete portal bridge structure over the IFI canal.
- A piled embankment transition zone from the bridge to a soft embankment (preload with vertical drains).

In anticipation of falsework settlement during the construction of the main

bridge a preload consisting of approximately 1m depth of stone was placed on the south side of the river. This activity was carried out prior to the award of the main contract.

Contractor Alternative

Early in the contract a steel composite bridge alternative design was proposed to replace the conforming 5 span main bridge. During negotiations with the client and Arup the contractor further developed the alternative design to extend over the full length of the Avoca Valley. The proposed alternative would then replace the 5 span main bridge, the piled embankment over the IFI landfill and the portal bridge structure over the IFI canal. The unique coincidence of the need to replace Wexford Bridge and the construction of the Avoca Bridge

at Arklow enabled the Contractor to negotiate a very favourable price for large steel composite decks, which were being built at virtually the same time. The proposed cost saving to the client was £100,000 with a reduction in time for completion by 6 months.

The reduced on-site construction time of the steel composite alternative realized significant overall project programme savings for the contractor and would permit the transport of fill material across the valley at an earlier stage in the contract.

The design of the alternative bridge was carried out by Kavanagh Mansfield Bullen (KMB) Consulting Engineers. Arup undertook a Class 3 independent verification of the design. Due to the demanding design programme required, a close working relationship was maintained between KMB and Arup during the design, verification and construction phases.

Deck Design

The bridge has a total length of 278m and consists of twin decks separated by a clear gap of 4.4m. The span configuration consists of a total of 10 spans ranging from 28.75m to 42m. The deck has four main plate web girders spaced at 3.9m. Intermediate cross bracing between pairs of girders is regularly spaced along the

length of the bridge. The deck slab is cast insitu concrete poured onto permanent participating formwork ('Omnia' Planks).

At all pier supports, except those either side of the main river span, a crosshead girder is incorporated with the main girders to reduce the number of bearings from four to two. An interesting feature at these crosshead girder locations is that the bearings are inverted so that any eccentricity which might arise would be transferred into the robust concrete pier rather than the highly stressed crosshead girder. A skirt plate cover is installed around the bearing to protect the PTFE surface from the ingress of dirt and grit.

Splicing of the main girders consist of a fully bolted connection. All bolts used within the deck are Tension Control Bolts Grade 10.9 in lieu of the commonly used HSFG bolts. The TCB system enables more reliable and rapid installation with fewer on site activities. The bolts were designed in accordance with BS 4604 Part 2 'Higher Grade'. The British Board of Agremont made an assessment in 1992 which found that TCB's are suitable for use in structural steelwork where HSFG bolts are acceptable. Note that BS 4604 Part 2 does not permit Higher Grade bolts to be sub-

jected to externally applied tension. The mechanism of the TCB is that the bolt shank is manufactured with a pre-determined torsional shear strength at its tip. During installation a non-impacting electric wrench is used to tighten the nut. When the torsional shear strength is reached the end tip of the shank shears off, leaving a fully tensioned bolt in position. Once the tip has sheared off the bolt cannot be reused or retightened. If bolts are ever required to be removed they must be drilled out.

Substructure Design

The substructure construction is in accordance with the conforming tender design. It consists of reinforced concrete abutments and blade piers. The abutments and piers are founded on driven precast piles with a SWL of 1300 kN (Lowry Piling). Modifications to the conforming tender design were required north of the river where the bridge extent was increased.

At the south abutment three rows of precast piles are installed behind the abutment structure in order to provide a gradual transition from the 'soft' embankment 'excavate-and-replace section' to the "hard" bridge structure. Originally this transition zone design consisted of the (stone) embankment.

However, due to uncertainty on the exact ending of the 'excavate-and-replace' section during detail design additional piles were incorporated. These piles are independent of each other and incorporate a 1m x1m cast insitu pile cap. Several layers of geogrid fabric are placed over the pile caps to provide a spanning medium for the embankment above.

The piers on the northside of the river are founded within the IFI landfill site. The ground conditions consist of 4m of made ground and a dense red silt material (iron oxide tailings). Elevated levels of some contaminants were present. The occurrence of low pH and high sulphates (Class 4 with zones of Class 5 according to BRE Digest 363, 1996 ref 4) was of particular concern for pile design. Six metres of made ground overlies the Alluvium which consist of an upper soft grey silty sand and a lower layer of soft peaty clay. Both layers are normally consolidated and highly compressible.

Coated precast concrete piles were adopted with a redundancy of 50% on the pile load capacity. The piles are designed to resist Class 4 sulphate conditions (ref 4) by use of sulphate resisting cement. The piles are then coated with a proprietary flexible bitumen protective system 'Consokote' in order to provide the additional Class 5 protection. Possible damage to the coating during driving was allowed for by predriving to the bottom of the made ground with an oversized steel mandrel and by incorporating a redun-

Figure 5 Bridge approach support piling

dancy in the pile design. The bases to the piers are also protected all round with a layer of 'Bituthene'.

In a similar manner to the south abutment, five rows of precast piles, with pile caps and geogrid, are installed behind the north abutment structure acting as a transition zone (see Figure 5). The construction of the north abutment had to be delayed until the lateral movement of the Contract 1A embankment had reduced to an acceptable amount. This movement was monitored by inclinometers and settlement plates strategically placed around the toe of the embankment.

Steelwork Fabrication and Delivery

The steelwork fabrication was carried out by Costruzioni Cimolai Armando in their Pordenone shops in north eastern Italy. The steelwork was transported by ship from Italy to Wexford where it was transferred to lorries for delivery to site. Cimolai were subcontracted by (Ascon) for the fabrication and erection of the steelwork on site.

Steel beam components for the Avoca river bridge arrived by road on large steel transporters, in lengths of up to 18 metres, and weighed up to 36 tonnes. Assemblies were bolted up on the ground and were erected in the prescribed sequence using a 200 tonne Eiger crane occasionally assisted by a 120 tonne hydraulic mobile crane.

Paint System

The paint system specified consists of a three coat system. The surface preparation consists of blast cleaning with chilled cast iron grit

- 1st Coat** - Zinc Phosphate Epoxy Blast Primer (2 pack) 100 microns
- 2nd Coat** - MIO Epoxy undercoat (2 pack) 150 microns
- 3rd Coat** - Polyurethane (2 pack) Finish 50 microns

The 1st and 2nd coats were applied in Cimolai's shops with the 3rd and final coat being applied on site. This paint system has a guarantee of no maintenance for up to 8 years with major maintenance not required until after 15 years.

Bridges over the Dublin to Wexford rail line

Both bridges over the rail line consist of single span structures. At Cooladangan the span is 7.5m. The deck consists of inverted T beams with a cast insitu infill slab. This bridge is best described as an extension to the existing tunnel-like structure for the crossing of the existing road over the rail line. At the Avoca Valley the span was 13m and the deck is similar to that of Cooladangan.

5.0 CONTRACT AWARD

Preconstruction phase Avoca River Embankments

Before the earthworks design could be finalised, and a definite method of construction could be specified, it was necessary to address a number of areas where the site investigations had shown that difficulties could be expected during construction. Among these was the problem of how best to build over the compressible layers of peat and soft silts on the south side of the Avoca, in the bottom of the valley, and how to construct the embankments over the materials dumped in the area of the site over the years which were now quite difficult to penetrate, but which overlay compressible deposits of peat and soft clays. There was also the question of what type of foundation to use to withstand the aggressive nature of the groundwater in the area north of the river. Groundwater has a pH as low as 4.6 and 20% of results indicating Class 5 sulphates (>6 gre) and a further 20% indicating Class 4 sulphates (3 to 6 gre, BRE Digest 363).

To expediate the project and avoid delays to the main contract 2 pre-contracts were let. Following successful preliminary trials carried out by Hambra Construction to determine whether or not it was possible to pen-

erate the iron oxide and carbon black deposits and install vertical drains, in March 1995, a contract was let to Stephen Byrne Civil Engineer Ltd of Gorey for the installation of vertical drains in these areas and the construction and monitoring of the necessary road embankment up to formation level in this area (Contract 1A). During the carrying out of the installation of the vertical drains under this contract Stephen Byrne encountered considerable difficulty in preboring through the top layers and maintaining the holes open to enable the vertical drains to be inserted. It was not possible to use one machine for both the predrilling and the insertion of the drains, and Byrne developed a special mandrel, to do the preboring which he mounted on a Hymac chassis, and which proved highly effective. The preloading and vertical drain contract somewhat overran its allotted time, but allowance had been made in the specification of the main contract to cover this contingency, and in the event, it did not cause any delay to

the main contract.

An examination of the depths of soft material on the south side of the river seemed to indicate that this material could be excavated and replaced by traditional methods. There was plenty of space available immediately adjacent to the embankment location to allow spreading of excavated material, and, provided that it was possible to keep an excavation open long enough to allow replacement rock or similar material to be placed, then this would most likely be the most cost effective and least risky method of providing a construction platform in this location. Following a tendering process, a contract for this work (Contract 1B) was placed with Wills Brothers, and successfully carried out in autumn 1995.

Tendering Process and Award of Main Contract

Tenders were sought for the main contract, for the construction of the Bypass proper and its intersections

and link roads, in April 1996 from a selected list of tenderers. The criteria for selection of tenderers for inclusion in the shortlist included relevant experience, technical expertise, especially in the construction of bridges, and availability of resources. Seven firms or consortia were invited to tender. Following an evaluation of the tenders, the contract was awarded to Ascon Limited, who had submitted the lowest conforming tender, and a time for completion of 36 months.

Following confirmation of insurances and bonding arrangements the formal Contract was let on 19th September 1996, and work commenced on site on 1st October. At the second monthly site meeting the Contractor indicated a willingness to settle all possible price and wages claims arising under Clause 67 of the contract for an agreed lump sum of £1.7 m + VAT. He also, simultaneously asked to be allowed to use a steel composite deck for the main Avoca River, offering a reduced contract duration of 30 months. Following a period of negotiation, the contract sum was agreed, with pvc buyout and a steel composite Avoca Bridge at £27.5m, incl VAT. The revised date for completion was agreed as 1st April 1999.

Construction methods

Structures : Foundation excavations for structures, which went ahead independently of the main earthworks, were carried out to depths of up to 9m using 30 tonne hydraulic excavators. Rock, where this was encountered, could generally be removed by these excavators, although hydraulic impact breakers were used to trim foundation excavations near to formation levels. 23 tonne articulated dump trucks were used to remove excavated material from the excavations.

Piling was mostly 350 x 350 precast concrete piles driven to a specified set. The Contractor (Lowry Piling)

Category	Material	Use
1	Gravel	Capping material
2	Import Rock	Self compacting rock for below water construction
3	Site Rock	Base of high embankments plus embankment layering
4	Suitable Soil	General embankment construction
5	Unsuitable Soil	Landscape mounds or off-site disposal

Table 2 Earthworks Categories

used a Junttan PM20 piling rig with a 60kN drop hammer to drive the majority of these piles. Bored concrete piles of 900 diameter required at the Ballyraine railway bridge were constructed by Murphy International using a Solmec auger mounted on a specially modified Cat 225 excavator.

Formwork for structures was mainly the proprietary 'Meva' system for walls and foundations. The panels were assembled in the largest panels practicable and lifted into position by crane. Makeup infills, upstands, splays etc, were formed using conventional timber shuttering. For general insitu deck construction the proprietary 'Cuplok' system of falsework was used in conjunction with 'Alform' beams.

Placing of concrete was generally carried out using a crane and skip. Where pours were large, concrete pumps were used. Filling at structures involved the placement of imported granular material behind and in front of abutment and wing walls. Where dozers and heavy compactors were not permitted or were not practicable in confined areas the Contractor used 20 tonne excavators to place and layer material, with compaction being achieved using 2.5 tonne doubledrum vibrating rollers. Plate compactors were frequently used around wing walls and where batters had to be formed.

The earthworks fleet consisted of 9 x 16 m³ motorised scrapers, pushed by 2x D9 bulldozers. In addition a

Caterpillar 825 compactor was utilised for compaction of fill. A fleet of 6 x 40 tonne articulated dumptrucks, loaded by 2 x 50 tonne hydraulic excavators. Two motorised graders were used to maintain haul roads.

6.0 MATERIALS

Earthworks Balance

Prior to commencement on site, the Contractor presented an earthworks balance which showed a deficit of 50,000 cubic metres of suitable filling material on the part of the work south of the Avoca river. It was apparent that the transport of material from the northern part of the works over the river to the southern end was a time critical element. There was never any question of the Contractor being allowed to transport any muck over the existing road system, and espe-

cially not through or near Arklow. It was therefore evident that he must bridge the Avoca, whether temporarily or permanently, as quickly as possible, and certainly by midsummer of the first year of construction. Because of the restrictions imposed by the available land take, and the bad ground conditions in the Avoca valley, the Contractors options were limited. Having examined how long it would require to construct the prestressed deck for even one of the twin decks proposed for the main bridge over the Avoca, and taking into account the speed of construction of a possible steel-composite alternative, the Contractor proposed an alternative bridge to the Client. This proposal was accepted, but, in the event, the deck of the first bridge was not finished in time to take full advantage of the potential of the concept within the first earthworks season. This, combined with his planned method of handling bulk earthworks, and the identified deficit on the southern end of the works prompted the Contractor to seek and make maximum use of a borrow pit at the head of the Avoca Valley on its southern side. Thus, although his first plan did not work out exactly as he had planned it, the contractor made quite good progress on earthworks by astute use of resources and opening up and using

a borrow pit to its optimum.

At the commencement of the second earthworks season in spring of 1998 the Avoca bridge was trafficable and the Contractor had full access to all areas of the work. He faced problems however due to the wet weather, which made scraper operations difficult. The Contractor adjusted his working methods to meet these conditions.

The volumes and locations of the various earthworks materials are shown schematically on Figure 6. The main difference between that predicted at tender and actual construction was in the volume of unsuitable material. A greater volume of suitable material was won from the cuts than originally allowed for. This can be explained by the moisture content values being lower than expected from the design interpretation of the site investigation, good handling of the materials by the contractor and the benefits of being able to work rapidly in good weather. In all the amount of excavated material not including topsoil was just over 1 million m³. The material required for embankment construction was 840,000 m³.

With the exception of Roadstone's quarry at Arklow there is a general lack of good quality gravel or crushed rock in the area. The net result was that 130,000m³ of capping material had to be imported a considerable distance from commercial suppliers.

Sources of Materials

Hardcore and Clause 804 material came from Roadstone Arklow, SM Morris, and Morrisseys of Rathdrum. Surfacing materials came from the Roadstone Arklow quarry and from Roadstone Enniscorthy. Readymix concrete was sourced from Morrisseys of Rathdrum.

Landscaping

Landscaping has been treated as a separate contract, with Wicklow County Council appointing their own specialist Landscaping Advisor, Terry Murray and Associates, and letting the contract completely separately from the Main Contract. The contract has been awarded to Coillte Teo, and work commenced on site in Oct 1998.

7.0 SITE ORGANISATION

The Engineers Staff

The Chief Resident Engineer was a member of the Arup staff. All other supervisory staff were employees of Wicklow County Council. At the peak of the work, in spring of 1997 to summer 1998, the maximum number of supervisory staff on the client side was 22. These included the Chief Resident Engineer, 2 Senior Engineers, (1 roads, 1 structures), a measurement engineer, 5 resident engineers {river bridge, all other structures, laboratory and materials control, roadworks (2)} 2 assistant engineers (structures, roadworks), 4 graduate engineers, 2 Clerks of works, 3 technicians, and an administrative assistant/typist. In addition, the services of a construction observer, who acted as a go-between with the local farming community were

available when required. As the work wound down, there was a great deal of staff leakage to other younger projects, and it became necessary to augment the staff on site on occasion with some members of staff from the consultants head office. The most important thing to be said about this staffing level is that it was entirely justified and necessary, and if anything, imposed a very heavy load on all concerned. It is to the great credit of all of the staff on site, that it is possible to say that the record keeping has been exemplary.

The Contractors Staff Contractors Resource on Site

The Contractor had the following supervisory staff on site; a project manager, three site agents, one each for earthworks, drainage and structures. In addition, a special site agent was deployed on Structure 8, the Avoca Bridge. There was a specific man employed as Health and Safety Coordinator, with responsibility for all matters relating to health and safety. A quality assurance manager periodically audited the quality assurance system operated by the Contractor on the site. The contractor, Ascon, has full QA Certification to ISO 9000. In addition to the site agents, the contractor employed one general foreman and five section foremen on the job. Over the two year and three

Figure 7 Clause 14 Programme V's As Built Programme

months of the contract work, an average of 180 men was employed on the site by Ascon, with a peak of 240 during the summer of 1998.

Progress Meetings

Progress meetings were held with the Client, Wicklow County Council, with representatives of the NRA present every month, at which the monthly Progress Report and the latest Certificate of Payment were discussed. Matters discussed at this meeting would include among other items in progress in the past month, adherence to programme, staffing, accommodation works, costs and budget matters, additional works requirements, variations to the works, dayworks and contractors claims.

Progress meetings were also held monthly with the contractor, usually on the same day as the Client progress meetings. These meetings discussed, in addition to progress, information sought by the contractor such as additional details and by the engineer such as method statements and such matters as variations, dayworks, contractors claims, in a general way.

Public Liaison

Wicklow County Council, as the Employer under the Contract, looked

after matters of dealing with the public and with property and landowners. In addition, the County Engineers Department met with local delegations as necessary.

8.0 ADDITIONAL WORKS

As part of the works, an artistic feature, in the form of two castles and a tapering wall was designed by Ken Meehan and Janet Doyle. It represents the history and culture of Arklow as a garrison town and the location of the country's best known mining area in past times, has been constructed near the Arklow slip lane on the Northern Interchange.

Public Lighting has been provided at the two interchanges, and warning signs have been erected which will allow traffic to be diverted off the bypass, in case of a serious traffic or industrial accident.

A Socio-Economic Study has been carried out in parallel with the building of the bypass. This study, carried out by Arup in association with Reid and Associates, Town Planners and Economic Consultants, is designed to allow comparison of the conditions in Arklow before the bypass was provided, with those which will ensue after the bypass is opened to traffic. Such matters as parking patterns and adequacy of parking provision, traffic

control, retail patterns and types of outlet present, stopping and passing traffic, have all been examined and benchmarked. While the present study covers only the conditions prior to the opening of the bypass, the benchmarking has been done in such a way that, it will be possible to compare the situation in three years time, when it can be expected that whatever new conditions the bypass may bring into being in the Arklow area will have become apparent, or will be emerging in a reasonably clear pattern. Thus, it should be possible to predict for other towns of similar size, or in similar circumstances, what the socio-economic effects of providing a bypass will be.

9.0 PROGRAMMING

At the first progress meeting with the Contractor on site in October 1996, he presented a programme for the works, as required by Clause 14 of the Conditions of Contract. The Engineer sought further details of resources and output which might allow that programme to be achieved. The programme was revised subsequently to allow for the influence of the use of a steel-composite Avoca bridge. The programme was adjusted at the end of the first earthworks season, in November 1997. The Summer of 1997 was relatively wet, and the building of the Avoca river bridge had been delayed. Ascon now brought forward a revised programme to completion, showing how they intended still to meet an opening date just prior to Christmas 1998. The project was officially declared open on Friday 29th. January 1999, by Mr. Noel Dempsey, TD, Minister for Local Government and the Environment, over two months ahead of the original revised programme date.

Figure 7 shows a summary of the Contractors Clause 14 programme and compares it with actual progress.

10.0 UNIQUE FEATURES OF THE PROJECT

The effects of Archaeology on the work were very substantial. Apart from the cost of the actual Archaeological dig, and the national importance of the finds, the extent of the Archaeological investigations and the period of time it took to carry them out very substantially disrupted the Contractors planned sequence of working, and the methods of working which he was able to employ. The presence of much of the Archaeological material only became evident during the stripping of topsoil.

The use of a steel-composite deck construction for the Avoca bridge allowed the work to be completed some six months earlier than might otherwise have been the case, had the originally planned prestressed concrete deck been adhered to. There was a saving of £100,000, in an overall cost of £3,200,000, in the cost of this element of the works. An economic analysis of the lifetime costs of the two types of structure showed them to be very similar. The steel alternative had very distinct programming advantages, and was chosen principally for this reason.

A considerable amount of research was carried out into the best piling system to adopt in the very difficult ground conditions prevailing in the Avoca Valley. On the one hand, there were materials dumped historically in the area which varied from pieces of metal vessels to domestic refuse, and from iron oxide in an aqueous suspension to carbon black, arising from industrial processes. The ground had a pH of as low as 4.6 in some locations, and very high sulphate contents. Steel piles were investigated in full, as were methods of cathodic protection for such piles. Trials were carried out with a mandrel, which showed that it would be possible to use precast concrete piles. Cast in situ concrete piles were

judged to be inappropriate for these site conditions. Finally following extensive test piling on site, and investigation of available protective systems for precast or steel piles, a decision was made to adopt precast concrete piles, coated with a protective layer of 'Consokote'. Because of the aggressive ground conditions, the bases to the piers for the Avoca Bridge are also protected all round with a layer of 'Bithuthene'.

11.0 CONCLUSIONS

The Arklow Bypass has been built to a high standard in a remarkably short time. What has been achieved would not have been possible without the absolute dedication of all of those involved. In particular, the Contractor, Ascon, must be given credit for the single-minded way in which the objective of meeting the programme, or of bettering it if possible was approached. It was a challenging project in many ways, with many innovations, and some impediments, but the relationships of all of the parties to the project were always courteous, and always co-operative. At no time during the carrying out of the work was there ever a hint of anything less than full co-operation towards the achievement of the common goal.

12.0 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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13.0 REFERENCES

- Ref 1 "Traffic Plan for Arklow" McCarthy & Partners 1968*
- Ref 2 RT 180 "Geometric Design Guidelines" An Foras Forbartha 1976*
- Ref 3 "Irish Road Sign Manual" National Roads 1997*
- Ref 4 BRE Digest 363 "Sulphate & Acid Resistance of Concrete in Ground" January 1996*

Some Statistics on the Arklow Bypass

11.6km dual carriageway
8km of minor roads
2 grade separated interchanges
13 bridge structures

Earthworks

1,257,000m³ of excavation (including topsoil)
274,396m³ imported material
193,524m³ of disposal

Drainage

25.3km of french drain
7.3km of spigot and socket pipes
446 manholes and catchpits
2.4km of steel culverts

Pavements

50,250m³ cl 804
313,313m² bitumenous paving

Concrete in Structures

20,336.77m³ of concrete

Steel in Structures

2760.19 tonnes of steel

ARKLOW BYPASS - DESIGN AND CONSTRUCTION

Appendix

FIGURE 3.5 STABILITY OF EMBANKMENT

JOB No.: S89303
 LOCATION: ARKLOW BY-PASS (8550m)
 DATE: 14.9.93

BOREHOLE/PIT No.:
 SAMPLE NUMBER:
 DEPTH: GLACIAL CLAYS

<<< CLAY >>>	FINE	MEDIUM	COARSE	FINE	MEDIUM	COARSE	FINE	MEDIUM	COARSE	>>>> COBBLES
<<<<<<	SILT			>>>>>>	SAND			>>>>>>	GRAVEL	

Figure 3.7 Grading curves for Arklow clays

ARKLOW BYPASS PLASTICITY CHART

ALL DATA

Figure 3.8 Plasticity characteristics for Arklow clays

ARKLOW BYPASS CBR vs M/C

* BASED ON $C_u = 25$ CBR

Figure 3.9a In-situ moisture content V CBR

Figure 3.9b Relationship of moisture content to optimum moisture content for CBR = 2

ARKLOW BYPASS MC/ OPT MC FOR CBR = 2

Overbridges

Location	Structure No.	Deck Width	Span Configuration (m)	Deck Type	Span-Depth	Abutments	Piers	Bearings	Deck Area (m ²)
IFI Access Road	10	1x1 carriageway with footpaths	14 / 21 / 21 / 16	RC voided cast insitu	18.3	RC supported on driven precast conc. piles	RC supported on driven precast conc. piles	Pot	842
Beech Road	11	1x1 carriageway with footpaths	24 / 24	Cast insitu cellular post tensioned	21.8	RC supported on pad foundation	RC supported on pad foundation	Pot at abuts. only	561
Lamberton Road	5	1x1 carriageway with footpaths	25 / 25	Cast insitu cellular post tensioned	22.7	RC supported on driven precast conc. piles	RC supported on driven precast conc. piles	Pot at abuts. only	635
Northern Interchange	12	1x1 carriageway with footpaths	25 / 25	Cast insitu cellular post tensioned	22.7	RC supported on driven precast conc. piles	RC supported on driven precast conc. piles	Pot at abuts. only	635

Underbridges

Location	Structure No.	Span Configuration (m)	Deck Type	Span-Depth	Abutments	Bearings	Deck Area (m ²)
Cooldangan Farm Access	1A	12.5m single span	Inverted precast T beams with cast insitu infill	17.9	Full height RC supported on pad foundation	Elastomeric each beam	415
Southern Interchange	2	16m single span	Precast U beams with cast insitu deck slab	14.5	Full height RC supported on pad foundation	Intermittent pot bearings	532
Coolgreany	3	24m single span	Precast U beams with cast insitu deck slab	17.2	Full height RC supported on pad foundation	Intermittent pot bearings	796
Johnstown Road	4	26.5m single span	Precast U beams with cast insitu deck slab	14.2	Full height RC supported on pad foundation	Intermittent pot bearings	565
Vale Road	6	26.5m single span	Cast insitu cellular post tensioned	22	RC supported on pad foundation	pot bearings	880
Arklow Rugby Club	13	17.2m single span	Precast U beams with cast insitu deck slab	14.4	Full height RC supported on pad foundation with precast piles for soft spot	pot bearings	572

Note: All underbridges were constructed as a single full width deck accommodating the full dual carriageway

Bridges over the Dublin to Wexford Rail Line

Location	Structure No.	Span Configuration (m)	Deck Type	Span-Depth	Abutments	Bearings	Deck Area (m ²)
Rail overbridge at Cooladangan	1	7.5 single span	Inverted precast T beams with cast insitu infill	15.2	Full height RC supported on pad foundation	Elastomeric strip	1495
Rail overbridge at Avoca Valley	7	13m single span	Inverted precast T beams with cast insitu infill	18.8	Full height RC supported on pad foundation	Elastomeric each beam	428

Note: All rail overbridges were constructed as a single full width deck accommodating the full dual carriageway

BRIDGE OVER RIVER AVOCA (STRUCTURE 8)

TOTAL LENGTH = 278m

TWIN DECKS EACH OF 14.5m WIDTH

MAXIMUM SPAN = 42m

STEEL GRADE MAIN GIRDERS = BS EN 10025 GRADE 355 J2 G3

FOUR MAIN GIRDERS SPACED AT 3.9m CENTRES

MAXIMUM PLATE THICKNESS = 60mm

MAIN GIRDER DEPTH VARIES FROM 1200mm TO 1700mm

MAXIMUM LENGTH TRANSPORTED = 26mm

TOTAL TONNAGE OF STEELWORK = 1300 TONNES

MAX. FILLET WELD SIZE = 15mm

BRACING TYPE B5

INTERMEDIATE
STIFFENER